

MEASURED SECTIONS →
OCCURRENCES

	UCLA 7329—Chicago Pass—JGG (1993)	Chicago Pass—Corsetti and Hagadorn (2000)	Chicago Pass—Jensen et al. (2002)	Chicago Pass—O'Neil et al. (2022)	UCLA 7333—Horodyski (1991-1992)	UCLA 7333—JGG (1993)	UCLA 7334—Hamill (1966)	UCLA 7334—BR (1995)	UCLA 7334—Jensen et al. (2002)	LACMHN 17130—Smith et al. (2017)	LACMNH 17130—Nelson et al. (2023)	Spring Mountains—Nelson et al. (2023)	UCLA 7331—Desert Range—JGG (1993)
base of middle member WCF	240		170		240	232	139		170		162	279	193
<i>Didymaulichnus miettensis</i>	200					210							
<i>Psammichnites gigas circularis</i>									136				
<i>Treptichnus pedum</i>	203			140		183							
top of third dolostone (3, Fig. 3)	185	104	112	130	absent	110	98	107		133		absent	
base of third dolostone (3, Fig. 3)	180	100	107	127	absent	104	91	102		129		absent	
<i>Treptichnus</i> isp. cf. <i>T. pedum</i>												120	170
cf. <i>Psammichnites gigas circularis</i>									95				
FAD of <i>Rusophycus</i> isp.									90				
FAD of <i>Treptichnus pedum</i>	165	80	97	110				80	90				
top of second dolostone (2, Fig. 3)	150	74	80	96		145	67	59	71		116	91	124
base of second dolostone (2, Fig. 3)	145	69	73	94	140	135	64	56	60		108	87	118
<i>Treptichnus</i> spectrum trace						128							
<i>Tulaneia amabilia</i>										64			
top of first dolostone (1, Fig. 3)	70	10	6	16		57	6	5	4	56	55	69	87
base of first dolostone (1, Fig. 3)	63	7	0	10	50	50	0	0	0	43	44	63	82
<i>Treptichnus</i> spectrum trace					20								
tubular body fossils					14	31							63
<i>Saarina hagadorni</i>											20	63	
<i>Tulaneia amabilia</i>					10	14				34	36	42	
top of basal dolostone	30			-2									
base of basal dolostone	24			-7									
top of Stirling Quartzite	0	0	?	0	0	0	0	0	?	0	0	0	0

stratigraphic heights in meters above top of Stirling Quartzite

REFERENCES TO SHADED CELLS

Fig. 11.1, 11.3; Jensen et al. (2002, fig. 5A)
 Jensen et al. (2002, fig. 5B)
 Fig. 10.7; O'Neil et al. (2022, fig. 2); Fig. 9.6
 Fig. 10.1
 Fig. 11.5
 Jensen et al. (2002, fig. 4C, 4D)
 Corsetti and Hagadorn (2000); Jensen et al. (2002, fig. 4A); Fig. 9.4; Jensen et al. (2002, fig. 4B)
 $\leq 532.83 \pm 0.98$ Ma (Nelson et al., 2023)
 Fig. 11.6
 Smith et al. (2017, fig. 1)
 Fig. 9.5
 Fig. 4.11-4.12
 Selly et al. (2020, fig. 1); Nelson et al. (2023, fig. 3A)
 Figs 5.1-5.6.1-6.7, 7.1-7.9, ?7.10-7.12; Smith et al. (2017, 3a-3g); Nelson et al. (2023, fig. 3B)